

**NATIONAL EVOLUTIONARY SYNTHESIS CENTER
YEAR 2 ANNUAL REPORT AND SITE VISIT DOCUMENT
DECEMBER, 2006**

NESCENT ANNUAL REPORT AND SITE VISIT DOCUMENT

NOVEMBER, 2006

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ANNUAL REPORT PROJECT SUMMARY

During year 2 NESCent realized its full functionality as a Center for the promotion of activities leading to a “grand synthesis” in evolutionary biology. The achievements of the Center are detailed in the subsequent sections on Science and Synthesis, Informatics, Education and Outreach and Administration. Briefly, they include:

- In year two the Center acquired a full complement of postdoctoral fellows and sabbatical scholars. This group contributes to a vital intellectual atmosphere at the Center, and has numerous interactions with visiting working and catalysis groups and the surrounding University communities. They have generated a wide variety of products, including publications, new databases, and analytical tools and software.
- We have hosted a variety of meetings over the past 12 months including 11 meetings of NESCent funded working and catalysis groups. We have also hosted several other groups, bringing a total of over 500 scientists to the Center. NESCent sponsored groups have already contributed to significant advances in evolutionary biology.
- We have constructed an outstanding Informatics program, with excellent staff and the full range of infrastructural services to support our scientific programs.
- The Informatics staff has supported in-house and visiting scientists in a variety of ways, and has partnered with external groups to submit two major grant proposals, thereby making progress towards achieving major cyberinfrastructure goals.
- The Center has participated in initiatives for data sharing, registry and repository, and is developing a plan, in conjunction with the Metadata Center of UNC Chapel Hill, to develop and implement a data sharing and repository strategy for evolutionary biology.
- Our Education and Outreach group has developed new focus for its activities. Efforts are centered on the communication of NESCent science, developing partnerships to improve and support evolutionary biology teaching and research at historically minority serving institutions, and to improve the teaching of evolutionary biology.
- The EOG group has completed a number of highly successful outreach activities, including co-sponsoring a symposium on modern evolutionary biology at the National Association of Biology Teachers annual conference and an extremely successful program at the Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science meeting.
- The administrative infrastructure of the Center has made enormous progress, with a new administrative database and redesigned website nearing completion, and a whole range of procedures, policies and activities developed that allow the Center administration to efficiently and effectively support NESCent sponsored science.

I INTRODUCTION – NESCENT IN YEAR 1

NESCent first received funding in December 2004. During the first year of funding attention was focused on hiring staff, renovating the physical space, establishing the submission and review process for proposals, establishing the Education and Outreach Group (EOG), and general outreach to the evolutionary biology community. Between January and October 2005 NESCent occupied temporary space. Postdoctoral fellows and sabbatical scholars began to arrive in July 2005, with a significant number first present in the fall of 2005. The first working group met in November of 2005 and the first catalysis meeting was held in January 2006 (off site). In November 2005 NESCent moved into its current and permanent space in the Erwin Mill Building.

Although the Center made significant progress in many ways during the first year of funding, a number of issues arose regarding NESCent governance. As a consequence in November and December 2005 Center leadership was restructured. In January 2006 Dr. Kathleen Smith assumed overall Directorship of NESCent, and Dr. Todd Vision accepted the position of Associate Director for Informatics, joining Associate Directors Drs. Joel Kingsolver (Science and Synthesis) and Greg Gibson (Education and Outreach). Although the EOG and Science and Synthesis programs were in relatively robust shape, the Informatics program, despite its critical role in NESCent's mission, had to be significantly reconstructed. In February a revised Informatics plan was submitted to NSF program officers and approved. At the same time, the revised governance structure for the Center was put into place with the formation of an Operations Committee consisting of the four Directors and an at-large member from each of the three Triangle Universities. During year two, the Science and Synthesis and EOG programs were further refined and the revised Informatics program was implemented. In the past 9 months, rapid progress has been made towards achieving the overall goals for the Center.

In this report we discuss the accomplishments of the Center during the second year of funding, with focus on activities between January and November 2006. We believe that NESCent is well on its way towards playing a central role in facilitating a grand synthesis in evolutionary biology. Below we will first provide an overall summary of NESCent's mission and provide examples of supported activities during year 2. Our aim here is to illustrate the ways that NESCent has successfully established itself as a center that promotes grand synthesis in evolutionary biology, and is in many ways unique.

Following that, detailed reports on activities and accomplishments for year 2 and goals for subsequent years of funding, are presented for Science and Synthesis, Informatics, Education and Outreach, and NESCent Administration. Detailed information on products, participants, meetings and activities are presented in the accompanying appendices.

II OVERVIEW OF ACTIVITIES – FULFILLING NESCENT’S MISSION

NESCent’s mission is to advance synthetic scientific research that addresses fundamental questions in evolutionary biology. Synthetic research in evolutionary biology occurs along a continuum in terms of the scope of the scientific questions, tools and disciplines that may be involved. At one end of the continuum, synthesis involves integrating available data and models to address important problems within a discipline. Such research is essential for quantitatively evaluating the current state of a field, revealing important general patterns and results, and identifying critical gaps and promising directions for future research. At the other end, methods and perspectives from multiple disciplines are combined to develop new tools for answering and even creating new fundamental scientific questions. NESCent plays an almost unique role in funding these kinds of synthetic and interdisciplinary initiatives in evolutionary biology. The most distinctive components of NESCent’s programs include the following:

NESCent’s emphasis on cross-disciplinary research brings together groups of scientists who might otherwise not talk to one another and provides a supportive and effective environment for stimulating synthetic research, individually and in collaboration. NESCent breaks down inter-institutional barriers to collaboration, provides an opportunity for evolutionary biologists with radically different expertise to work together on a daily basis, and houses a group of resident scholars who can drop what they are doing, pick up new ideas and run with them.

Catalysis meetings provide a novel mechanism for bringing together diverse research communities and cultures to identify common interests, while working groups provide an opportunity for scientists to work together intensively on grand challenge questions over a several-year period. NESCent’s work is community driven and can respond to pioneering ideas from the evolutionary biology community at large that don't otherwise have a means to be realized. We take great pride in offering top notch facilities, informatics assistance and logistics support so that scientists need concern themselves with only one thing: synthetic evolutionary biology.

NESCent provides state of the art informatics tools to visiting and in-house scientists. We aim to take the lead in developing new analytical tools for evolutionary biology. Further, NESCent provides a neutral ground to promote consensus building and to develop standards for data and analytic tools and interoperability of software.

Finally, NESCent has created a new model for training in evolutionary biology. Here 14-16 postdoctoral fellows with diverse interests work side-by-side with sabbatical scholars and a host of local faculty. These postdoctoral fellows are provided numerous opportunities to interact with hundreds of visiting scientists in any given year. The breadth of exposure to evolutionary biology is unmatched anywhere.

The assessment of NESCent’s success will be the demonstration that important advances in synthetic evolutionary biology research have been made possible by association with and support from NESCent. We believe such demonstrations are already possible and offer several cases of important scientific breakthroughs resulting from our first two years of funding.

1. NESCent brings together scientists from diverse fields in order to produce major conceptual breakthroughs.

The first working group to meet at NESCent was organized by **Paula Mabee and Monte Westerfield** and was entitled **“Towards an Integrated Database for Fish Evolution.”** The aim of this group was to attack one of the most exciting but intractable questions in biology: how the genome is modified over evolutionary time to produce the diversity of anatomical forms (phenotype/morphology). This group brought together two distinct communities: members of the Tree of Life effort for Cypriniform fish (CToL), studying the phylogenetics and evolutionary radiation of this group of fish, and the ZFIN project, which is assembling data on the relation of genetics and phenotypes in zebrafish. This working group is addressing this grand challenge question by synthesizing knowledge from various biological levels encompassed in development (e.g. DNA sequence, gene expression, regulatory networks) with evolution (phylogenetic relationships) and ecology. To synthesize this work, a common language (ontology) for anatomical terms (phenotypes) and for evolutionary relations must be established. NESCent has facilitated this project not only by providing the means for the group to meet, but by taking an active role in the practical and conceptual issues of ontology development. NESCent Informatics staff members have been deeply involved in this project, and in June 2006 a joint grant for further development of the project was submitted by NESCent and the PI's of this working group. By supporting this project, NESCent has facilitated development of the first evolutionarily based anatomical ontology, and has made possible the very exciting collaboration between the model organism/biomedical community and the systematic and evolutionary biology community. This effort in ontology construction is already identified as an effort of broad and fundamental importance, and Mabee has been contacted by numerous individuals who seek to modify the ontology developed with NESCent's support for their own systems.

“I want to thank you and the NESCent staff, again, for making magic happen. When Paula Mabee and I started a conversation a couple of years ago about our crazy idea to link phylogenetic and genetic studies, we decided that we needed a place to meet and travel support for a think tank. NESCent was the perfect vehicle. Our three workshops at NESCent allowed a small group of evolutionary biologists, molecular geneticists and bioinformaticians to meet and develop methods to integrate these previously disparate fields. It was hard work. First, we had to learn enough of each other's vocabulary to carry on a conversation. Then, we had to think through new methods for integrating these very different kinds of data and, finally, we had to develop plans to build the actual database and the necessary informatics tools. This endeavor was remarkably successful; we have already submitted a manuscript describing this new idea and a grant proposal to fund the database and tool development. NESCent was the necessary catalyst. As the National Evolutionary Synthesis Center, NESCent has more than fulfilled its role for us by providing the right environment for synthesis of a new field.” Monte Westerfield

2. NESCent scientists collaborate with Informatics staff in order to produce significant analytical breakthroughs.

Evolution is a spatiotemporal process that is structured by the geographical history of planet Earth. Geographical information systems (GIS) are software that supports the storage, retrieval, mapping, and analysis of geographic data. Within evolutionary science GIS can be used to explicitly integrate population genetic and phylogenetic models of multiple taxa with data describing present and past environments and climate. **NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow, David Kidd** has focused on the development and application of GIS tools for evolutionary biology and in a recent editorial in the *Journal of Biogeography*, Kidd and

Ritchie (2006) outlined a manifesto for GIS application in evolutionary science. Kidd is using GIS to collate fluvial history models for Mesoamerica that will be compared to patterns of freshwater organism biodiversity. To facilitate this work, Kidd and NESCent resident programmer Xianhua Liu have designed and implemented a software package, the *GeoPhyloBuilder* extension for ArcGIS software. *GeoPhyloBuilder* creates a spatiotemporal GIS data model from a tree file and associated data describing the geographical location of tip entities. 3D visualization can be easily created using the ArcSCENE viewer. The software is applicable to any discipline that uses tree models to classify spatial entities. For example Kidd has illustrated the distribution of extant and extinct fishes across historical and current rivers through time. Kidd emphasizes that software quality and efficiency has been greatly enhanced through the use of a professional programmer provided by NESCent. *GeoPhyloBuilder* v1.0 is scheduled for release in Jan 2007 at the 3rd Biennial Conference of the International Biogeography Society, Tenerife. Already the journal *Molecular Ecology* has expressed interest in using the data model to store data submitted to the journal and interest in this tool has also been expressed by some collaborative phylogeography groups, for example the NESCent "Patterns of Biodiversity in Madagascar" catalysis meeting. *GeoPhyloBuilder* version 2, to be developed at NESCent during year 2 of Kidd's postdoctoral position, will support phylogenetic networks, a more sophisticated data model and some analysis tools; exact development priorities will depend on version 1.0 user feedback. NESCent has not only supported a highly creative and productive postdoctoral fellow, but has facilitated the development of what is likely to be a landmark software package.

"...when I read of your plan for a phylogeography database on evoldir, I was quite delighted as something of this sort is long over-due." Loren Rieseberg. Chief Editor, *Molecular Ecology*

"...sounds brilliant - we need to be able to do sophisticated analysis of emergent patterns. Ultimately it could be obligatory to put the information into your system in the same way that journals demand GenBank accession numbers." Dr Paul Sunnucks, Senior Lecturer in Zoology, Molecular Ecology Research Group and Australian Centre for Biodiversity: Analysis, Policy & Management, Monash University, Melbourne

3. NESCent provides a rich environment for opportunistic collaboration among resident scientists.

During the spring of 2006 NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow **Derrick Zwickl** and **Sabbatical Scholar Paul Lewis** embarked on a novel and fortuitous collaboration. While Lewis was performing independent research on methods for evaluating the adequacy of models of DNA sequence evolution, he obtained results suggesting that the most common approach for accommodating rate variation among sites (termed discrete gamma-distributed rate heterogeneity, or dGRH) was inadequate for the analysis of large datasets. In an effort to understand the basis for these surprising results, Lewis and Zwickl began discussing the theory behind dGRH and alternative modeling approaches. These discussions continued over a period of weeks and gradually this continued interaction allowed them to reach an understanding of the limitations of the dGRH method. As an alternative, they settled upon a technique that they termed FLEX, due to its increased flexibility relative to dGRH. Lewis and Zwickl each implemented a form of the FLEX model in their respective software (*Phycas* and *GARLI*, respectively), moving the work beyond the purely theoretical.

Evaluation of the FLEX model in the two programs was particularly interesting because it allowed for comparison under two distinct statistical frameworks (Bayesian in *Phycas* and Maximum Likelihood in *GARLI*). Although both frameworks are widely used in

phylogenetic applications, the performance of novel modeling approaches is rarely evaluated simultaneously in both. Initial tests of the FLEX approach made it clear that it provides a large improvement in model fit relative to dGRH in both statistical frameworks. Due to its clear superiority, Lewis and Zwickl believe that the FLEX model may in time replace dGRH as the default approach for modeling rate variation among sites.

Lewis presented their initial joint work investigating the performance of the FLEX model at the joint annual meeting of the Society for the Study of Evolution at Stony Brook in June 2006. A publication detailing further evaluation of the model is planned. The model is available for use by interested researchers in the open-source GARLI analysis software. Research on models of rate heterogeneity had not been planned by Lewis or Zwickl while at NESCent. The project was entirely opportunistic, arising from ongoing discussions over a period of weeks. NESCent brought the researchers together, and allowed their continued interaction free from other academic responsibilities.

4. NESCent promotes the answering of important evolutionary questions through the support of novel data assembly and analysis.

Theoretical models predict that the mating system of a species should be either primarily selfing or primarily outcrossing. However, more than 40% of insect-pollinated flowering plants reproduce through a mixture of selfing and outcrossing (mixed-mating). Why are mixed-mating systems so common in plants and what are the consequences of this for diversification and trait evolution in flowering plants? **A Working Group organized by Susan Kalisz and Mark Johnston, “Understanding the Paradox of Mixed Mating”**, is working to resolve this gap between current theoretical predictions and empirical evidence. The first two meetings of this group generated progress in three main areas. Discussions about the intersection of theory and data stimulated new directions for theoretical models that incorporate both genetic and ecological features. A second major task has been to expand and systematize an existing database on selfing rates in plants. The database, already including more than 1300 mating system estimates, is incorporating data on inbreeding depression, life history, floral morphological traits and other information, chosen to integrate with the ecological, genetic and evolutionary parameters relevant to theoretical model predictions. A third emphasis is the use of phylogenetic adjustments for testing the relationship of selfing rate to other features, given that the selfing rate may itself evolve rapidly. This is key to testing the hypothesis that selfing is an evolutionary ‘deadend’ that reduces subsequent evolutionary diversification.

In their third meeting in early December, 2006, this group outlined manuscripts on the following topics:

- Theoretical reasons to expect stable intermediate rates of self-fertilization
- Conceptual and experimental tools for understanding how pollination ecology influences the evolution of plant mating systems
- Variable inbreeding depression and evolution of selfing rate
- Phylogenetic evidence for a flower size and number tradeoff
- Correlates of the mating system: biogeography, morphology, ecology
- Is the distribution of selfing rate bimodal—bias in the data?
- Clonality, population structure and inbreeding depression
- Is self-fertilization a dead end?
- Relation of inbreeding depression to rate of self-fertilization
- Patches, pollinators, dispersal and self-fertilization

In addition the group has been invited to contribute reviews to both *American Naturalist* and the *Journal of Evolutionary Biology* and has submitted a successful symposium proposal on Mixed-Mating Systems for the Annual Meeting of the Society for the Study of Evolution, to be presented in New Zealand in June 2007. This extraordinarily productive group has requested and will be provided with funding for a 4th meeting.

NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow Joe Hereford is conducting a synthesis and meta-analysis of experimental studies of local adaptation in natural populations. His aim is to document the frequency and magnitude of local adaptations in order to address the fundamental question of how common local adaptation is in nature. Using a defined set of criteria for types of study systems, experimental protocols and fitness measures, Hereford has identified and collated 73 studies of local adaptation in natural populations for a variety of plant and animal species. His preliminary analyses suggest that local adaptation is quite common: in more than 70% of all cases, local populations have greater fitness in their native habitats than all non-native populations. On average native populations have 20-30% higher fitness than non-native populations, but there is substantial variation in this native advantage among species. There is little evidence thus far for publication bias in the analyses. Surprisingly, increasing gene flow among populations has no detectable effects on limiting the extent of local adaptation. These results are important for understanding local and regional patterns of biological diversity, the evolutionary potential of natural populations to respond to environmental change, and the resistance of native populations to biological invasion. Hereford is currently working on two papers from this project and has initiated a collaboration with current postdoctoral fellow Jason Hoeksema. The opportunity to pursue such synthetic and independent research as a postdoctoral fellow is almost unique within evolutionary biology. Hereford's project is nearing completion and he has accepted an NSF Postdoctoral Fellowship at the University of Maryland to start in January, 2007.

5. NESCent provides a stimulating environment for new theoretical breakthroughs.

Genetic mutations occur in all organisms, and many mutations impact fitness, but what are the relative frequencies of harmful, neutral and beneficial mutations, and how strong are their effects on fitness? These questions are at the heart of a wide range of fundamental genetic and evolutionary issues, from genetic medical disorders and the molecular clock to the nature of adaptation and the evolution of sex. The recent explosion of data on DNA sequence variation within and between populations provides a powerful new resource for exploring the fitness consequences of mutations. During his year at **NESCent Sabbatical Scholar Adam Eyre-Walker** has developed new theoretical models that estimate the frequency distribution of fitness effects. A major advance of these models is that they account for potential effects of demographic (population size) changes. Eyre-Walker has applied this new method to a dataset of human genes. Most non-synonymous (amino acid-altering) mutations have mildly deleterious effects, with an average effect on fitness of a few percent; less than 10% of mutations have strong effects. This work was recently published in *Genetics* and highlighted on *Faculty of 1000*. Eyre-Walker has also extended these methods to estimate the fraction of base substitutions between species that are due to adaptation, and is applying this approach to datasets on sequence evolution in bacteria (papers in press and submitted to *Molecular Biology and Evolution*).

6. NESCent catalyzes new collaborations and interactions.

The island of Madagascar has exceptional floral and faunal diversity. It is unrivaled in the degree of taxonomic endemism: for example more than 95% of all primate, reptile and amphibian species on the island are found nowhere else on Earth. Madagascar's historical isolation and remarkable geological and environmental heterogeneity have likely both impacted its biodiversity. The relative contributions and interactions of isolation and environment for different taxa are unknown, but this is key both to understanding Madagascar's biological history and future responses to habitat destruction, invasive species and climate change. **A Catalysis Meeting, organized by Anne Yoder and Claire Kremen, "Patterns of Biodiversity in Madagascar,"** brought together a diverse set of theoretical and empirical biologists with expertise in a wide array of taxonomic groups important to Madagascar. The meeting explored three main questions. First, when did different taxonomic groups first arrive on Madagascar and how does this impact the present-day biological communities? Second, how do geology and local climate affect patterns of diversity and endemism? An important insight gained from discussion of these environmental effects for diverse taxa is that the integration of GIS tools, environmental niche modeling and coalescent methods are a potentially powerful way of incorporating historical and environmental components into analyses of diversity. Third, how can evolutionary understanding inform conservation priorities and planning in Madagascar? A key point of discussion here is whether and how historical information about geographic centers of diversification and refugia can be incorporated into algorithms for selecting nature reserves for conservation.

This catalysis meeting has already produced many new scientific collaborations. A working group proposal has been submitted to NESCent for the December 1 deadline that proposes to examine mutualisms in Madagascar, and was a direct result of this meeting. Additional new collaborations include: a group that is examining the question of developing environmental layers for deep-time slices; a group exploring bridging present-day niche modeling with allele distributions using coalescent models and methods; a group performing a coordinated examination of arrival times across a broad array of taxa at deep phylogenetic levels (i.e., across animals, plants, and fungi), with the view of examining historical patterns of community assemblage; and a group that will explore the effects of geological substrate and climate on patterns of biodiversity distribution, with a focus on areas of high local endemism.

"The NESCent location and support allowed an extremely diverse set of biologists, theorists, paleontologists, and conservation planners to gather in a user-friendly environment that is ideally designed to foster communication. This is true for both large-group discussion and presentation, as well as small break-out group formats. The staff support was incredible. Indeed, logistics were almost effortless, allowing the participants maximal time to focus on the task at hand. Without NESCent's financial, logistical, and infrastructural support, I can not imagine that this large group of specialists (nearly 30 participants) would have been able to come together simultaneously, and make such rapid progress in the exchange of ideas. It was a fantastic experience." Anne Yoder

III NESCENT ACTIVITIES AND ACCOMPLISHMENTS, YEAR 2

A. SCIENCE AND SYNTHESIS

In the previous section we highlighted NESCent's overall goals and illustrated several ongoing successful projects. Here we report more specifically on the scientific activities of the Center in year 2. In order to achieve our aim of promoting high quality synthetic activities in evolutionary biology Science and Synthesis at NESCent has focused on three major goals during the past year: 1) to attract, fund and support high-quality, important and diverse synthetic activities; 2) to establish effective and open application and review processes; 3) to ensure the productivity and impact of NESCent scientific activities. During this second year at NESCent, we have begun the transition from developing and implementing the systems and processes for attracting, evaluating and supporting scientific activities, to doing the science and evaluating its impact.

1. Scientific Activities

Our Fall 2005 call for proposal (deadline 15 October 2005) attracted 55 proposals, and resulted in 18 awards, including 6 postdoctoral fellows, 4 sabbatical scholars, 4 working groups and 4 catalysis meetings. Our Spring 2006 call for proposals (deadline 15 June 2006) for working group and catalysis meeting proposals only, attracted 18 proposals and resulted in 8 awards including 6 working groups and 2 catalysis meetings (see Tables 1-3 for summaries and Appendix A.1 for all awards to date).

Table 1. Winter 2006 proposals and awards

Type	Proposals	High Priority	FIFA	Do Not Fund	Offer	Accept
Postdocs	22	7	7	7	7	6
Sabbaticals	8	3	3	3	4	4
Working Groups	14	4	3	3	4	4
Catalysis Meetings	11	3	7	7	4	4
Total	55	17	20	20	19	18

Table 2. Summer 2006 proposals and awards

Type	Proposals	High Priority	FIFA	Do Not Fund	Offer	Accept
Working Group	10	5	5	0	6	6
Catalysis Meeting	8	1	6	1	2	2
Total	18	6	11	1	8	8

Although the Science Review Board makes recommendations, final decision on funding was made by the Operations Committee based on these recommendations. In practice we have funded all proposals ranked "High Priority", and a few ranked "FIFA" (fund if funds available). Our criteria for funding proposals in the latter group have included balancing

funding among fields, and increasing the number of proposals from members of under-represented groups.

NESCent awards in 2006 address a diversity of evolutionary questions and approaches ranging from plant functional genomics and gene network variation, through the evolution of body size and primate life histories, to biodiversity in Madagascar and the evolutionary origins of chemoreception (Table 3). Complete award information is provided in Appendix A.1.

Table 3: NESCent Awards in 2006.

Activity	Project Title
Catalysis Meetings	Genomics and Adaptive Radiation
	Biodiversity in Madagascar
	Evolutionary Genomics of Poeciliid Fishes
	Evolution in Contemporary Human Populations
	Origins of Chemoreception
	Selfish DNA and Vector-Borne Disease
Working Groups	A Novel Journal Concept for Evolutionary Meta-Analyses
	Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium: Evolution in ACTION
	Fossil and Molecular Estimates of Divergence Times
	Evolutionary and Functional Plant Genomics
	Evolutionary Informatics
	Cis-Regulatory Evolution
	Gene Network Variation
	Evolution of Body Size
	Integrative Algorithmic Methods for Historical Biogeography
	Primate Life Histories
Postdoctoral Fellows	A Framework for the Study of Cultural Evolution
	Evolution of Mammalian Fossoriality
	A Phylogenetic Database for Comparative Biology in Land Plants
	Parallel Morphological Diversification in Sister Fish Faunas
	New DCM Methods in Biogeography
	The Relative Importance of Biotic vs. Abiotic Local Adaptation
Sabbatical Scholars	Designing an Evolution Curriculum for Elementary Students
	Chiton Phylogeny and Comparative Phylogeography
	A Community Approach to Evolutionary Theory
	Evolution in a Spatial Context: a Synthesis of Theory and Review

Collectively, NESCent awards to date address a diversity of fundamental questions in evolution, systematics and comparative biology. To evaluate this diversity we have classified each award in terms of subject areas at different levels of biological organization (e.g. molecular, organism, population, phylogeny) and methodological approach (e.g. meta-analysis, theory, informatics). We have a good representation of awards at different levels of organization with 6 that are primarily molecular, 5 organism, 12 population, 18 phylogeny and 3 education. By classifying awards in terms of their primary and secondary subjects we can assess the extent of cross-disciplinarity (Table 4). More than 2/3 of the awards involve multiple levels of biological organization (off-diagonal elements in Table 4); many of these combine phylogenetic perspectives with other levels of analysis. This illustrates how NESCent is facilitating interdisciplinary synthetic research in evolutionary biology.

Table 4. Cross-disciplinarity of NESCent awards.

	Molecular	Organism	Population	Phylogeny
Molecular	1	1	4	6
Organism		2	4	9
Population			4	4
Phylogeny				6

Since the opening of the new NESCent facilities in November 2005, we have established a vibrant and collegial community of in-house scientists. This community currently includes 13 postdoctoral fellows (2 more to arrive by Jan 2007), 4 sabbatical scholars, and several visiting scientists from Triangle and other Universities (Appendix A.2). This community now has a regular seminar series (Appendix A.3), a journal club, small discussion groups, active intranet communications, and a host of new social traditions.

In 2006 we supported and hosted 29 meetings (Appendix A.4.) These included 11 meetings of catalysis and working groups, including meetings by all of the groups funded in the first round, 3 advisory, 2 education, and 1 informatics meeting (Appendix A.5). In addition we have hosted 12 meetings of various groups involved in evolutionary synthesis, 6 of these supported in part by NESCent or Provost funds (Appendix A.6) and 6 of these hosted at NESCent with no funds provided (Appendix A.7). These meetings have brought over 500 visitors to the Center.

We have established a mentorship program for the postdoctoral fellows, in which each fellow is assigned a faculty mentor from the NESCent Operations Committee. The mentor and fellow meet regularly to discuss research plans and progress, point the fellow to relevant faculty and lab groups in the Triangle, aid in professional development, and whatever else may be useful to the fellow in helping them succeed at NESCent and beyond. We have also developed a series of presentation and discussions about professional development for the postdocs, led by the EOG team (see the EOG Section of the report).

2. Application and Review Processes

We developed and implemented an on-line application system that has been used during the last two rounds of proposals (deadlines 15 Oct 2005 and 15 June 2006). We have established the guidelines for proposals, criteria for evaluation, and conflict of interest policies, all of which are available on our web site. We have established a regular schedule for applications, with deadlines of 15 June and 1 December each year.

We expanded the Science Review Board to 18 members, to increase our expertise in bioinformatics and computational biology, and maintained the excellence and diversity of the Board in terms of field, rank and gender (Appendix A.8). We are currently adding 5-6 new members to the Board to maintain continuity as founding members begin to rotate off at the end of their 3-year terms starting next year.

We improved our on-line review and panel meeting systems for use by the Science Board. Our system involves written evaluations of each proposal by 3-4 Board members, and discussion, recommendation and a summary of each proposal at the Board meeting. Following final decisions by NESCent, the reviews and Board summary of each proposal are made available on-line to the applicant.

We developed and implemented a new type of scientific activity, Triangle working groups. These working groups primarily involve faculty local universities, specifically Duke University, the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill and North Carolina State University. Proposals for Triangle working groups undergo the same review and evaluation process as other proposals, but are funded by contributions from the Triangle universities, not by our core-NSF funding. This approach increases the engagement of the Triangle university community at NESCent, and leverages our funding to enhance NESCent's productivity.

We have established application, evaluation and support processes for NESCent and NCEAS (National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis) to jointly sponsor working group projects that integrate evolutionary and ecological synthesis. We recently (October 2006) awarded the first such project to organizers Karen Strier, Susan Alberts and Patricia Wright, Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories.

3. Findings and Products

The first scientific activities funded by NESCent began in the summer and fall of 2005, just over one year ago. As a result many of the outcomes and products of these activities are preliminary. Nevertheless, based on the reports by NESCent participants through October 2006 we can clearly document the success of synthetic scientific research supported by NESCent (see Appendix A.9).

Sabbatical Scholars:

The sabbatical scholars have produced 10 papers published or in press, including articles in *PNAS*, *Science*, *TREE*, *Evolution*, *Genetics* and *Molecular Biology and Evolution* resulting from their work at NESCent. One additional paper and one book (Oxford University Press) are submitted or nearing submission. Scholars have made 16 presentations at universities and scientific meetings on their NESCent research.

Sabbatical scholars have also made important contributions to evolutionary software and databases, although most of these are not yet ready for general release. These include software for phylogenetic analysis (PHYCAS), evolutionary extensions to database schema (Chado), and a database for information on programs in evolutionary biology at Minority Serving Institutions.

Postdoctoral Fellows:

Our first cohort of postdoctoral fellows has now been at NESCent for one year of their two-year fellowships. As evidenced by their annual reports the postdocs are making good to excellent progress. To date these fellows have published two research papers and given eight presentations at universities and national and international meetings on their projects at NESCent. Several important new software tools have already been developed by NESCent postdocs, including tools for visualizing spatiotemporal phylogenies (*GeoPhyloBuilder* 1.0 for ArcGIS) and a new interface for phylogenetic inference software (GARLI).

Working Groups and Catalysis Meetings:

Although only two of our working groups has met more than twice, each of our first cohort of three working groups have already been highly productive, yielding six in press or submitted papers, 11 presentations, and 3 major grant proposals. All three working groups from year 1 involve database development projects that are still ongoing.

Four catalysis meetings occurred during the past year. The main goal of a catalysis meeting is to bring together different research communities to explore evolutionary questions of common interest, and to generate specific new directions for further research. These groups report a variety of new collaborations that have resulted from these meetings; at this early stage these collaborations have not generated specific products.

4. Demographics of NESCent Funded Scientists

NESCent funds proposals on the basis of scientific quality. We aim to provide opportunities for scientists that are members of under-represented groups, and encouraging applications from members of such groups is a priority. Below the major demographic patterns of our funded scientists are summarized, and further data are provided in appendices A.10 - 14.

Table 5. Demographics of Lead Principle Investigators of Meetings Funded in 2006

	Total	Male	Female	White, non-Hispanic	Asian	African-American
NESCent working group	10	9	1	9	0	1
Catalysis meeting group	6	4	2	5	1	0
Triangle working group	2	0	2	1	1	0
Total percentages		72%	18%	83%	11%	6%

Table 6. Demographics of Sabbatical and Visiting Scholars at Center in 2006

	Total	Male	Female	US Citizen	International
Sabbaticals Funded 2005	5	5	0	3	2
Sabbaticals Funded 2006	4	3	1	4	0
Triangle and Visiting Scholars 2006	6	2	4	5	1
Percent NESCent funded		88%	12%	77%	12%
Total percentages		66%	33%	80%	20%

Table 7. Demographics of NESCent Postdoctoral Fellows at Center in year 2

	Total	Male	Female	US	International	White, non-Hispanic	Asian	African American
Funded 2005	8	4	4	5	3	7	0	1
Funded 2006	6	4	2	5	1	5	1	0
Total percentages		57%	43%	71%	29%	86%	7%	7%

In 2006 there were 259 attendees at NESCent funded meetings. 230 were from institutions in the United States and 29 came from addresses outside the United States (a number of these individuals were U.S. citizens). Attendees from the U.S. included individuals from 31 different states (including the District of Columbia and Puerto Rico) (Appendix A.13). Participants from outside the U.S. came from 14 countries (Appendix A.14). Although we have been instructed to limit travel funding that is provided to foreign scientists, evolutionary biology is an international science, and we believe it is important to include the very best scientists to address any given question. Each PI is requested to justify the inclusion of an international scientist, and these individuals are asked if alternative travel funds are available before paying for their travel on the NESCent core grant.

Table 8. Participants in NESCent Funded Meetings 2006

	Total	Male	Female	US	International
Advisory (SAB, SRB)	35	21	14	32	3
Education	40	23	17	39	1
Catalysis Meeting	104	86	18	88	16
Working group	80	57	23	71	9
Total percentages		72%	23%	88%	12%

5. Science and Synthesis: Goals and Challenges for Years 3-5

The goals for Science and Synthesis for the coming year are to continue to develop and diversify our portfolio of scientific activities at NESCent and to ensure their productivity and impact. Plans for awards in years 3-5 are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Proposed Number of Awards in Years 3-5.

Type	2007	2008	2009
Postdoctoral fellow	6	5	0
Sabbatical scholar	4	4	3
Working groups & Catalysis meetings	8	8	0

There are several priorities for developing scientific activities in the coming year.

1. We need to ensure that we are doing proper outreach to the evolutionary biology community as a whole. NESCent directors and EOG staff have attended a variety of meetings, in some cases with an exhibition booth, and at other more informally. These meetings have included, the Society of Integrative and Comparative Biology, the Evolution

meeting (joint meeting of Society for the Study of Evolution, Society for Systematic Biology and American Society of Naturalists), and the Bioinformatics Open Source Conference, (see full list in Appendix 15). We have posted advertisements for our calls for proposals at the websites of the Society for Study of Evolution (SSE); the Society for Integrative & Comparative Biology (SICB); the Society for Vertebrate Paleontology (SVP); the Society of Systematic Biology (SSB); the Botanical Society of America (BSA); the Evolution Directory (EvolDir); and the Paleobotany list serve and the journal *Evolution*.

We have invited the governing boards of the major evolutionary biology societies to hold meetings at NESCent in order to establish links and enable discussions of how NESCent can best serve their constituencies. The Society for Systematic Biology has already scheduled a meeting for March of 2007 and the American Society of Naturalists is in the process of doing so. The editorial board of the newly revived journal, *Evolutionary Biology* will hold its first meeting at NESCent in January 2007. Finally we hope that our newly designed web site and a series of planned NESCent newsletters will bring NESCent science and opportunities to the attention of the community. However, we must continually ensure that we are doing all we can in community outreach activity.

2. Projects awarded to date represent a wide array of levels of organization, taxa and approaches (Tables 3 & 4), but greater representation in certain areas is needed. For example, there are relatively few projects on evolutionary perspectives on developmental systems, especially for working groups and few in the general field of integrative organismal evolution. We also hope to increase projects that address applied aspects of evolution (but see below). To address these needs we are expanding representation of these fields on the Science Board (e.g. Todd Streelman and Tony Zera have recently agreed to join the Board), enhancing our presence and presentations at relevant scientific meetings (SICB, SSE, and other conferences in these areas), and discussing project possibilities with potential project leaders.
3. The number of outstanding proposals we are receiving for sabbaticals at NESCent is more limited than for the other activity types (e.g. see Table 1 above). On the recommendations of the Senior Advisory and Science Boards, we have made the duration and timing of sabbatical visits more flexible, as this is an important consideration for many potential applicants.
4. Our original plan was to fund postdoctoral fellows for 2 years only. The postdoctoral fellows requested that we, like NCEAS, consider funding for a third year. We have decided to do so on a trial basis. We expect that postdoctoral fellows requesting such funding will provide a detailed justification for the third year of funding, and present the results of their work, justification and future plans to our Science Review Board, who will advise the Directors on whether or not the request should be granted. This procedure is similar to the one followed by NCEAS.
5. Our original plan was to support catalysis meetings only during the first year of funding. At the strong recommendation of our Senior Advisory and Science Boards, we have continued to consider and award catalysis meeting proposals. While the catalysis meetings thus far have been very effective in generating new communication and potential collaborations, evaluating the productivity and payoff from these meetings is a challenge. Our approach for the coming year is to only consider catalysis meetings that have extraordinary potential to address fundamental evolutionary issues and that contribute to other priorities at NESCent. For example, in our last round of proposals we funded only two catalysis meetings: one ("Selfish DNA and Vector-borne Disease") brings together molecular biologists and evolutionary biologists from both basic and applied perspectives to address

how evolutionary biology can inform the use of transgenics in managing vector-borne diseases; the other (“Origins of Chemoreception”) explores commonalities in the evolutionary origins of chemoreception across the entire tree of life and is a strong example of combining integrative organismal biology with phylogeny.

6. We plan to encourage and support a project involving a distributed graduate seminar that addresses a major question in evolutionary biology. Such a project would involve a coordinated series of parallel graduate seminars at different universities, each led by different faculty members. This activity would allow synthesis at a larger scale than individual working groups and provide opportunities for greater graduate student involvement. We are currently discussing potential topics and organizational structures, with the goal of soliciting proposals for this in summer 2007 or winter 2008.

B. INFORMATICS

The NESCent Informatics program has two broad goals. The first is to provide support to the Center's scientific visitors and working groups. This includes providing basic electronic collaboration tools as well as the development, use and integration of databases, analytical tools and other computational technologies to advance their scientific aims. The second goal is to help build cyberinfrastructure that will enable evolutionary biologists to fully exploit the information-rich discipline that biology has become. This latter goal requires leveraging the energies and talents of the open source programming community to build easily-used, extensible, interoperable software components for evolutionary analyses; developing means to put biological knowledge into digitally meaningful form; and training the evolutionary biology community to fully realize the potential of these tools. NESCent has made substantial progress on each of these fronts in the past year. Below we report on Informatics activities with regard to NESCent sponsored science, cyberinfrastructure initiatives in evolutionary biology, and building basic infrastructure for informatics within NESCent.

1. Support of NESCent Sponsored Science

One of the attractions of NESCent to many in the community is the ability of the Center to provide software programming support and expertise. NESCent has met the challenge of providing expert informatics support to the variety of currently sponsored projects.

Providing such support is not a trivial undertaking, as a dozen or more projects may need support at any one time. For each project brought to the Center a considerable investment of time is often necessary to gather requirements, design, implement, test, and iteratively refine the final product. In order to maintain the vibrant Science and Synthesis activities of the Center, the lion's share of the effort of the Informatics staff supported by NSF core funding must be devoted to sponsored research. However, by supporting sponsored science in this way, we ensure that the Center's informatics efforts are of immediate utility to the scientific community.

In year two the Informatics group contributed to a diverse array of projects generated by our in-house scientists. Many of these initial projects have or may lead to the development of major resources for the evolutionary biology community. Major examples of supported projects include the following:

NESCent phylogenetics consultant Jim Balhoff, who is supported by Duke University's Institute for Genome Science and Policy, designed a graphical user interface to the phylogenetic software package GARLI in support of the work of NESCent postdoctoral scholar Derrick Zwickl. This pioneering software allows maximum likelihood phylogenetic trees to be computed for very large datasets (hundreds or thousands of leaves) on a desktop computer by using a novel optimization strategy. The graphical user interface makes this powerful method accessible even to computational novices.

GUI Project Manager Xianhua Lu (from the NESCent Informatics team) worked with postdoctoral scholar David Kidd to develop a beta version of his Phylogeographic Information System, which was profiled above.

A database was developed for the working group "Understanding the Paradox of Mixed Mating Systems in Plants." A prototype web interface is currently being developed for data curation and dissemination of their data collection by NESCent Informatics staff.

NESCent Informatics Consultant Nassib Nassar worked with sabbatical scholar Owen McMillan to develop a data model for phenotype and genotype variation that is interoperable with other data model components of the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD). The resulting database together with a prototype web-application is being refined and will eventually replace the existing ButterflyDB (*Heliconius*) database. GMOD is discussed in more detail below, as this project has been a test case for a major cyberinfrastructure initiative to enable the evolutionary biology community to manage and disseminate genomics data from evolutionary model organisms.

NESCent informatics staff members have worked extensively with the working group "Towards an integrated database for fish evolution." Jim Balhoff has worked to extend Phenote, an open source curation tool for assigning ontology terms to describe phenotypes in a common syntax using common controlled vocabularies. This work has advanced Phenote towards meeting the requirements of the system proposed in the joint grant application (see below) and of others in the evolutionary biology community, including former sabbatical scholar Quentin Cronk.

2. Cyberinfrastructure for Evolutionary Biology – Major Initiatives

In addition to providing the core support for the Center and its sponsored science as described above, NESCent is charged to be at the forefront of the development of cyberinfrastructure in evolutionary biology. However, given the resources necessary to fully develop a major cyberinfrastructure initiative, the Center is very limited in what can be achieved using core funding. Thus, in order to meet our goal of developing major cyberinfrastructure programs, it is critical that NESCent establish partnerships with the broader scientific and informatics communities, and seek outside funding to take cyberinfrastructure initiatives beyond the planning and prototype stages. In addition, because of the breadth of possible initiatives, the Center must be strategic in its choices of what projects to undertake, looking for synergies between cyberinfrastructure goals and support of sponsored science wherever possible.

The Center leadership believes that NESCent must remain responsive to new ideas from the evolutionary biology community; community suggestions are obtained through the proposal process, an informatics "white paper program" and via Center-sponsored meetings and hackathons (see below). At the same time, the Center must also have a clearly articulated method to decide which initiatives we adopt and support. In the revised Informatics Plan (February, 2006), a process for establishing these priorities in the future was set forth (see summary of process in Appendix B.1) and will serve as our guide in years 3-5.

In year 2 our activities focused on cyberinfrastructure initiatives that were discussed in the February 2006 revised Informatics Plan, and which arose, in part, from the "MetaData Meeting" held in Wilmington NC in June 2005. This meeting had broad community participation and provided recommendations to NESCent for cyberinfrastructure in three areas: Genomics, Phenotypes and Phylogenetics/Biogeography.

Genomics

A major recommendation of the MetaData Meeting's Genomics Working Group was to provide support for the implementation of evolutionary model organism (EMO) databases. The evolutionary biology community lacks capacity to manage fully the overwhelming volume of high-throughput structural and functional genomic data that is now being

generated in a wide variety of organisms. NESCent aims to play a major role in assisting the community in accessing such tools.

The Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) project, which is supported by grants from the NIH and USDA, is an open-source collaborative that provides a flexible, standardized data model uniting a number of diverse but interrelated datatypes commonly managed by model organism databases (MODs), and a host of intercompatible web and user interface components, that allow users to browse and annotate sequence and map data, curate literature, etc. GMOD has managed to attract a large community of active developers from some of the major MODs (FlyBase, Gramene, SGD, TAIR, WormBase) and the open source bioinformatics community at large. It is clear that GMOD could be a valuable resource for the EMO community: it is economical and efficient to implement, is widely supported, promotes intercompatibility among databases, and incorporates a great deal of hard-won experience in its design.

NESCent has partnered with the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) project to further develop their data model for evolutionary datatypes (organisms, phenotypes, collections, population variability, and phylogeny), to develop web applications for accessing these types of data, and to provide user support for adoption of the GMOD platform for evolutionary model organisms. In year 2 NESCent's activities in partnership with GMOD have included the following:

The semiannual meeting of GMOD developers was held at NESCent in June 2006. Attendees discussed ways to harness the expertise of the evolutionary community for refinement of GMOD and to promote the adoption of GMOD by the evolutionary community.

A proposal was submitted by Lincoln Stein, Ian Holmes and Todd Vision to the NIH Program "Continued Development and Maintenance of Software" in May 2006. If funded, this will, among other things, provide staff at NESCent to improve user support for GMOD (including development of tutorials, documentation, customized assistance in planning and implementation, providing feedback to developers). The project also aims to enhance the GBrowse genome annotation browser to broaden its functionality for population diversity data. The proposal received a priority score in the top 6%, leading us to expect that it will be funded starting in April 2007. This project will add 1 FTE to our informatics group. Therefore it will allow us to increase the impact of the Center's cyberinfrastructure efforts by building upon our existing capacity without pulling resources from our core Informatics staff. In the meantime, we have employed the services of an independent consultant, Dr. Brian Osborne, who is helping to recruit and train the permanent help-desk staff as well as gathering and documenting requirements and use cases from the evolutionary model organism community. If the NIH proposal is funded this position will be a full time position at NESCent that will provide advice, help and training to the evolutionary biology community in GMOD resources.

Phenotypes

The Phenotypes Working Group at the 2005 MetaData Meeting identified phenotype ontologies as a critical piece of cyberinfrastructure needed to navigate relations among specimens, taxa, anatomical concepts, and developmental genetic knowledge. As detailed above, NESCent, in collaboration with a sponsored working group led by Paula Mabee and Monte Westerfield, has made substantial progress in facilitating this goal. In addition, sabbatical scholar Quentin Cronk and phylogenetics consultant Jim Balhoff have worked

extensively on this topic. NESCent's work on the Mabee/Westerfield project has led to a partnership with the National Center for Biomedical Ontology (NCBO), which is part of the NIH-funded network of National Centers for Biomedical Computing. The NCBO hosts a number of different ontology development projects, develops infrastructure for ontologies and ontology-typed data, formulates and promotes principles of ontological rigor, and engages in education and dissemination. In particular, along with the Mabee/Westerfield working group, we have worked extensively with those responsible for the Phenotype and Trait Ontology (PATO), which is intended for describing traits or phenotypes that can be measured either quantitatively or qualitatively.

NESCent hopes to continue its contribution to the field of standardized descriptions of phenotype using ontologies via a grant submitted together with Mabee, Westerfield, Vision and others to the NSF Databases and Infrastructure program. If funded, this project will implement the plans being actively developed by the Mabee/Westerfield working group. Although the working group has made major progress on the conceptual basis for a database that will enable studies on the genetic and developmental regulation of evolutionary morphological transitions, the task of developing and applying ontologies for taxa and phenotypes in a large clade of fishes is enormous. The grant will support this work and will allow us to develop a suite of database and web-interface tools that will enable researchers to investigate relationships between evolutionary phenotypes and those seen in genetically characterized developmental mutants of zebrafish. The role designated for NESCent is to develop the database and web interface tools to support the research queries desired by the community.

These tools and approaches hold great promise for studies in other branches of the Tree of Life, and so we have proposed a series of educational workshops on Ontologies for Evolutionary Biology in partnership with the NCBO. This effort also takes advantage of our partnership with Data Central at the San Diego Supercomputer Center, which will provide long-term hosting and management support for the database. The project would start in June 2007 and add two developers to the NESCent Informatics staff.

We feel this example provides a model for how NESCent can leverage its limited resources and unique strengths to have a major impact on the field. It is a pioneering cyberinfrastructure initiative, perceived by the community to be at the core of the Center's mission, that is being pushed forward by the energies and talents of sponsored scientists, enabled by partner organizations, and takes advantage of the resources of NESCent to prototype ideas and seek outside funding for their full realization. As with the GMOD project discussed above, this project would add capacity to NESCent's core Informatics staff, and would not require a diversion of resources from support for sponsored science.

Phylogeographic Informatics

One of the major cyberinfrastructure challenges identified by the Phylogenetics and Biogeography working group at the MetaData Meeting was the task of integrating the large amount of georeferenced information about phylogenetic relationships, organismal distributions, and environmental conditions past and present. NESCent is fortunate in having an expert and dedicated in-house scientist to help drive this cyberinfrastructure initiative. As discussed above, postdoctoral fellow Dr. David Kidd has been developing software to store phylogeographic data (e.g. phylogenies, distance matrices and networks, hybrid zones, distributions and fossil records) and enable analysis and visualization of phylogenies within an ArcGIS geographical information system (GIS) framework. NESCent

informaticist Xianhua Liu has been working with Dr. Kidd to prepare the first release of *GeoPhyloBuilder* in January 2007.

Phylogenetics software

The Phylogenetics and Biogeography working group also advised the Center to "leverage and promulgate what can be done with existing [phylogenetic] resources, data, and tools." In order to meet this goal, the Center sponsored a "phyloinformatics hackathon" that was co-organized by Hilmar Lapp, Arlin Stoltzfus and Aaron Mackey and took place December 11-15, 2006, at NESCent. Hackathons bring together software developers for intense, focused collaborative software development sessions with face-to-face interaction. Hackathons have played an important role in the development of well-engineered, interoperable open-source tools in BioPerl and similar projects of re-usable toolkits. A hackathon is also a very cost-effective way for the Center to spur the development of cyberinfrastructure resources that are truly community-owned and also introduce many of the leading software developers in the world to NESCent's staff, activities and resources.

The focus of this first NESCent hackathon was on the development of Bio* open source software tools in the area of phyloinformatics. Approximately two dozen participants, including many of the top phylogenetics and Bio* software developers attended, including Mark Holder, Paul Lewis, and David Swofford (of CIPRES), Sergei Kosakovsky-Pond (of HY-PHY), Bill Piel (of TreeBase), Jason Stajich (of BioPerl), and Richard Holland (of Biojava). The development targets of have been open to input from the evolutionary biology community at large, and include many multi-software analysis workflows suggested by the resident scholars at NESCent. To ensure focus and maximum impact of the development activities, the participants narrowed down this list to six high-priority use-cases based on those encountered most often and for which phylogenetic workflows are well established. Among these were identifying gene family orthologs and paralogs, estimating divergence times, determining concordance among phylogenies and reconciling trees, detecting the signature of positive selection in a phylogeny of coding sequences, and identifying functional sites in protein families using evolutionary traces.

The hackathon was highly successful on multiple levels. First, a substantial amount (> 15,000 lines) of freely available working source code was produced, significantly advancing each individual toolkit towards representing phylogenetic data types and seamlessly interfacing with the analysis programs most commonly used in phylogenetics. The most mature of the toolkits, BioPerl, filled gaps in all use-cases that were selected. Second, the source code was documented as it was written, and is publicly accessible in a form that gives clear instructions to end-users for how to construct the respective workflows. Third, the hackathon facilitated extensive interactions between developers from the toolkit communities and experts in phylogenetic analysis algorithm development who would otherwise not have met. Some of these interactions will continue long after the hackathon and potentially provide long-term benefits to both communities. Fourth, the hackathon resulted in work on data exchange standards in evolutionary analysis that may have a lasting impact on the field as a whole.

Two participants of the hackathon have submitted a tutorial proposal for the ISMB conference in 2007 that will teach part of the results from the hackathon to a broad community of biologists and computational scientists in comparative genomics. If accepted, the Center will help with developing the curriculum. Finally, results of the hackathon will be included in the evolutionary informatics summer course to be developed by NESCent. An article on the hackathon from the online journal *bioInfOrm* is included as Appendix B.5.

In September 2007 Dr. David Swofford will be joining NESCent as a Senior Scientist. Swofford has been recruited to the Institute for Genome Science and Policy at Duke University as a Research Professor. As part of this appointment, Swofford will devote approximately 20% of his time to NESCent. Swofford is one of the preeminent developers of phylogenetic software in the world and his role at NESCent will include continuing research in phylogenetic analysis, collaborating with NESCent scientists on software and phylogenetics projects, advising the Directors on potential informatics initiatives and projects, primarily in the field of phylogenetics, and participating in informal workshops and summer courses in phylogenetic analysis, software and programming.

Population Genetics Software

A second hackathon is currently being planned for spring 2007 in the area of Population Genetics software development within the framework of the R open-source statistics platform. Dr. Martin Morgan of the BioConductor project is currently working with NESCent Informatics staff to organize this event.

Digital Data Repository for Evolutionary Biology

One effort that has been an important component of NESCent's mission since its inception is in the area of digital data sharing and archiving. This goal remains a high priority. Our goal is to establish a repository for heterogeneous digital datasets to ensure long-term preservation and to promote resource discovery and reuse. The focus of the repository, at least initially, will be on published datasets. A number of journal editors and society officers have already informally agreed to require deposition as a condition of publication once the digital data repository is sufficiently developed. Design principles that are guiding this effort include:

- Providing tools and incentives to researchers for deposition of data
- Streamlining data deposition and metadata generation for researchers, including single-stop deposition of data in relevant domain-specific community databases (for DNA sequences, trees, images, etc).
- Accommodating intellectual property of journals and researchers
- Providing metadata and web services to allow data-harvesting by third-parties
- Interoperability with data registries/repositories in allied fields (e.g. ecology, paleontology, genetics)
- Using open and well-supported technologies
- Adopting a self-sustaining business model with a plan for long-term data stewardship

To achieve this ambitious goal, NESCent has partnered with experts at the MetaData Research Center (MRC) at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, directed by Dr. Jane Greenberg of the School of Information and Library Sciences. Over the past several months NESCent and MRC staff have been intensively researching requirements and evaluating related projects and technologies. We have also been in discussion with stakeholders such as journal editors and society officers. In the short term, in order to capture data being published in evolutionary journals, but with minimal burden on authors, NESCent will establish a DSpace repository (www.dspace.org). The editors of *American Naturalist*, *Evolution* and the *Journal of Evolutionary Biology* have agreed to make deposition of published data a requirement if and when such a repository exists. In order to put in place a project plan for long-term development and a business model for this

repository, NESCent and MRC are planning two workshops to be held at NESCent within the next 6 months. The first meeting will include a variety of experts from related digital data sharing efforts, particularly those for "small-science" where there exist similar challenges of data heterogeneity, lack of existing metadata standards, and the need for researcher-generated metadata. The second workshop will involve stakeholders from the evolutionary biology community and will be used to reach consensus as to how the repository will operate and to draft the outline of one or more external grants to support further development, if that is deemed desirable. In the meantime, one Informatics staff member is being recruited specifically for this initiative and will be paid out of core grant funding. In addition, we have participated in a NSF sponsored initiative on data sharing and data repositories organized by the Ecological Society of America (Cliff Duke, primary organizer). We have tentatively agreed to host a meeting of this group in the spring of 2007, in part to make sure our efforts are fully consistent with the continuing efforts of this community.

Other initiatives

NESCent has also completed its involvement with a number of cyberinfrastructure initiatives that were launched prior to the Center's reorganization.

Interoperability between specialized evolutionary data repositories

Morphobank (at SUNY Stony Brook) and Morphbank (at Florida State University) are both NSF co-sponsored databases designed to manage data and images for use in taxonomy, morphometrics, comparative anatomy, and phylogenetics. Beginning in March 2005, with financial support from NESCent, the two databases began to collaborate towards a common data model with the goal of enabling data sharing and client interoperability. The data model specifies the types of data to be stored and how that data is accessed through web services and other protocols. With NESCent funds, Morphobank extended their data model to capture Morphbank-specific concepts such as "views", and aspects relating to taxonomy and specimens. Morphobank also used the funds to complete development of a phylogenetic data editor that is fully operational over the web. Authors can upload and download Nexus files, media (including 2D images, CT scans, etc.) and taxonomic information. The images can be affiliated with taxonomies and with cells in a matrix to demonstrate morphological homology statements. The funding provided to Morphobank was used to enhance the system's support for Life Science Identifiers (LSIDs), which allow persistent and resolvable references to objects in Morphobank and other relevant biodiversity data sources.

A NESCent hosted meeting in February of this year, led by the Taxonomic Databases Working Group (TDWG) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), resulted in a broad community agreement to support and further define the LSID standard for interoperability of biodiversity objects on the web. Further infrastructure to support interoperability between the databases would include third-party user authentication, so that collaborators could maintain common accounts on multiple systems. How to implement such a service, and NESCent's potential role, is still a topic of active discussion.

Evolutionary Bioportal

An early initiative of NESCent, through its partnership with RENCI, was development of a BioPortal, a portable open-source platform through which researchers have easy-to-use web-GUI access to a large suite of scientific software applications, and the computational power is delivered by transparent use of TeraGrid resources. The Bioportal, which is now being

independently developed by RENCI, was first released in May of 2006 (<http://www.tgbiportal.org/>). The Bioportal bundles into one coherent software stack tools such as Globus, MyProxy, PISE, the Taverna workflow manager and the Virtual Data Language scripting environment. At the time of our previous annual report, it was the intention of NESCent to continue this partnership by hosting an instance of the Bioportal that would be maintained by RENCI but customized and extended by NESCent specifically for the evolutionary biology community. While this would clearly be worthwhile if it could be done well, there are concerns about the investment that would be required in order to effectively maintain the resource and to enhance the user interface to the level that would be necessary for widespread adoption by the evolutionary biology community. The Senior Advisory Board, in their most recent review of the Center's activities, strongly indicated that this should be given a lower priority than other initiatives being undertaken by the Center. We continue to stay apprised of technical developments in RENCI's Bioportal, as well as the San Diego Supercomputing Center's newly developed Biology Workbench, and we will provide consultations to both groups regarding evolutionary biology software packages for inclusion. However, we do not foresee further allocation of core resources to this initiative in the coming year.

3. Training Initiatives

A major part of the mission of NESCent is to build human capacity in evolutionary informatics through a variety of training activities. Training activities related to the GMOD and phenotype ontology initiatives were described above. In addition, NESCent Informatics is committed to supporting and developing a series of summer courses for further training in informatics.

In the summer of 2006 NESCent co-sponsored (with NCEAS) the annual month-long intensive summer course in analytical paleobiology run by the Paleobiology Database, coordinated by John Alroy. Twelve students, primarily early-career graduate students, studied simulation modeling and data analysis methods in community paleoecology, quantitative biochronology, diversity curves, speciation and extinction, morphometrics, and phylogenetics. Currently, a summer course on phyloinformatics is being planned by NESCent for 2007 in partnership with William Piel of TreeBase/CIPRES.

4. Informatics Infrastructure

The above sections summarize the scientific accomplishments of our Informatics program in year 2 of funding. However it is also important to note that NESCent entered its second year of funding with minimal infrastructure in informatics and significant effort went into recruiting staff and building infrastructure. In addition, as is summarized in the Administrative discussion below, the Informatics staff have devoted a significant percentage of their time in recent months in providing support to the administrative capacity of the Center (administrative database, survey and website construction).

Building the Informatics team

After Vision's appointment as Associate Director for Informatics in January 2006, steps were taken to recruit a full-time Assistant Director of Informatics to oversee the day-to-day operation of Informatics. The Center recruited a highly qualified Assistant Director, Mr. Hilmar Lapp, who officially joined the Center on May 1st. Lapp has an M.S. in Biology (with a minor in Computer Science). He was previously a Bioinformatics Group Leader at the

Genomics Institute of the Novartis Research Foundation and has over 10 years of experience with data modeling, software architecture, and algorithm development for biological applications, including over 10 peer-reviewed publications in the field. He is a core developer of BioPerl, lead developer of BioSQL and BioPerl-DB, and has served on the board of the Open Bioinformatics Foundation since 2001.

Subsequently staff members have been recruited to the two positions that were most urgently needed to provide informatics support to working groups, resident scientists and Center administration. The position of web and graphical user interface (GUI) project manager was filled by Dr. Xianhua Liu in August. Dr. Liu has a Ph.D. in Ecology with an emphasis on eco-informatics, and has four years of postdoctoral experience working on ecological and taxonomic applications using Java and ArcGIS. The position of database project manager was filled by Dr. Surya Dhullipalla in October. Dr. Dhullipalla has an M.S. in Software Engineering and a Ph.D. in Organic Chemistry, plus six years of experience as a software engineer, systems consultant and database developer, with over two years of experience with genomics applications. These personnel join the existing system administrator, Jon Auman. In addition, the Center has employed contract programmers to work on specific projects, as discussed above. An organizational chart of NESCent's Informatics staff is provided in Appendix B.2.

General Informatics Infrastructure

In addition to personnel, the Informatics program has made significant progress in establishing underlying Informatics infrastructure which is critical to fully supporting NESCent-sponsored science. These infrastructure initiatives to support science include:

- Launching of a Wiki-based intranet which allows all NESCent resident scholars and staff to add and modify shared content.
- A help ticket system has been rolled out to efficiently manage, track, and respond to user requests and IT problems.
- Audio-visual equipment has been upgraded to better serve our hosted meetings.
- Major hardware and software purchases have been made to better meet the computing, server, and storage requirements created by the science undertaken at the Center.
- Purchase of 16 nodes on the Duke Shared Cluster Resource (DSCR) and installation of a number of software packages being used by the sponsored scientists. The DCSR is a large Linux cluster (consisting of several hundred nodes) used for high-performance and parallel computing.
- Additional long-term server room space is being acquired on the Duke Campus through the Office of Information Technology (OIT) in order to ensure that the servers are kept in a temperature-controlled environment, have backup power, and can take advantage of an OIT-managed tape backup system.
- To effectively support the electronic collaboration and workspace needs of sponsored scientists, especially of catalysis meetings and working groups, we created a comprehensive package, named 'IT@Meetings', which consists of several components including mailing lists, a wiki-type electronic collaborative space, extensive help-desk support during meetings, and access to Center computing resources, including access to the Duke high performance clusters.

Reaching the scientific goals of many if not most sponsored scientists will entail the development of databases, web applications for making those databases available to the evolutionary biology community, and other software. We have created informatics infrastructure on several levels to effectively support those activities.

We have made considerable progress in clarifying, during the proposal process, the nature and extent of the informatics support that can be provided to sponsored scientists. For example, we now provide documentation about what types of informatics support can be provided (Appendix B.3). The Associate and Assistant Directors for Informatics also review proposals and provide guidance to the Science Advisory Board and the Operations Committee to ensure that the Center can meet its informatics support commitments and that sponsored scientists are informed if modifications to the plans are necessary or desirable.

Data and Software Policy

A new Data and Software Policy was approved by the Operations Committee (OC) in order to ensure that the products of sponsored research are put into the public domain following best practices. The policy sets out roles for the Informatics staff as well as those for sponsored researchers. These policies assure that all data and software developed under NESCent's sponsorship are accessible from web-based interfaces, made available in a timely manner, and are sufficiently documented using appropriate standards and conventions. The specific policies are posted on the website and are included here as Appendix B.2.

5. Goals and Challenges for Informatics in Years 3-5

There are three overarching goals for Informatics in years 3-5. The first goal is to provide individually-tailored support to our sponsored scientists. Some projects require only consulting while others require more intensive effort. A challenge in meeting this is the need to streamline the amount of effort invested in each project by improving our ability to empower researchers to accomplish more of their own informatics objectives. We think the most effective approach to achieving this will be training. Already, at the request of the postdocs, we will begin to offer training for resident scientists in use of the R statistical platform. Additional training opportunities will be identified in year 3.

The second goal for Informatics in years 3-5 is to continually advance the five strategic cyberinfrastructure initiatives started in year 2:

- Reusable database components for genomic and natural diversity data,
- Application of ontologies to phenotypic studies,
- Integration of geographic data into phylogenetics,
- Libraries for combining evolutionary analysis tools and data into automated workflows, and
- A repository for preservation, discovery, sharing, and synthesis of published digital data in evolution.

These strategic initiatives are long-term commitments that will occupy our attentions through year 5, and beyond. There are a number of challenges in moving these initiative forward: maintaining strategic partnerships (e.g. with GMOD and the MetaData Research Center); leveraging our efforts on sponsored science projects that have a high degree of synergy with these initiatives; providing leadership to the community when there is insufficient incentive among academic collaborators; and aggressively pursuing

opportunities for external funding to build capacity. In year 3, we anticipate contributing significantly to the planning of the NSF Plant Science Cyberinfrastructure Collaborative, which will help move us forward on a number of these strategic initiatives.

In year 3, we anticipate a number of specific deliverables, such as the software development outcomes of the two planned hackathons (on phylogenetic and population genetic software libraries) and the release of *GeoPhyloBuilder*. The development of extensive user support infrastructure and evolutionary software components for GMOD will start to impact the community in years 3 and 4. In years 4 and 5, encouraged and eventually enforced by evolutionary biology journals, researchers will start to deposit their data in a digital repository, and the scientific community at large will begin to use that resource for synthetic research. Pending funding, we will develop software for curating, storing, and disseminating ontology-based annotations of evolutionary phenotypes beginning in year 3 and continuing through the first release of the public database for the project in year 5.

The third overarching goal is to train the next generation of evolutionary biologists so that they can fully exploit the cyberinfrastructure that is being developed. The evolutionary biologist of the future should be able to discover, retrieve and reuse published evolutionary data for their synthetic research; have the ability to integrate machine-readable phylogenetic, geographic and phenotype data in order to ask new kinds of questions; and efficiently construct complex software workflows for large scale analyses. We anticipate offering a new summer course in phyloinformatics starting year 3 and recurring annually.

In addition to those mentioned above, the Informatics team faces three broad challenges as we look forward. The first is accomplishing the ambitious agenda described above with the small staff available. It will take a strong sense of focus, a regular review of priorities, streamlining support (as discussed above) in order to master this challenge without frustration on both the side of the Informatics team and on the side of those it supports.

The second challenge is to maintain the necessary high level of expertise in the fast-paced and extraordinarily broad field of informatics. The Informatics team itself needs to constantly stay abreast with the changing landscape of technologies (application frameworks, engineering best-practices, programming paradigms and languages, user-interface designs and capabilities, communication protocols, and data exchange standards) in order to establish NESCent's informatics program as a reputable source of best-of-breed solutions and trustworthy leadership. In addition, the diversity of expertise required by the various initiatives places high demands on the current Informatics leadership. Our solution is to supplement this, wherever possible, by partnerships with appropriate academic experts. For the digital data repository initiative, we have done this by specifically recruiting Dr. Jane Greenberg of the UNC MetaData Research Center.

A final and perpetual challenge is maintaining our responsiveness to the Informatics needs of the evolutionary biology community in the face of rapidly expanding data sets, technologies, and theory. We census the community through NESCent's sponsored science, informatics sponsored meetings and hackathons, a variety of partnerships with individuals and other organizations, and our Informatics white paper program; we have set in place methods to evaluate and prioritize potential projects. Now that we have achieved fully functional Informatics program, we need to ensure that the avenues for input from the community are sufficient, and our means of evaluation are appropriate to allow our program to provide the level of leadership and service we and our community expect.

C. EDUCATION AND OUTREACH

The NESCent Education and Outreach Group (EOG) has continued to build its presence and lay a foundation for productive outreach activities. This report summarizes a number of specific projects that we believe have had a significant impact, while an appended spreadsheet (Appendix C.1) comprehensively lists the specific activities delivered by the two program managers, Drs. Kristin Jenkins and Jory Weintraub. In light of a key meeting of many of the principals in the evolution education community held at NESCent in mid-July, EOG has undertaken a revision of its mission for the next three years. This has also entailed a reassessment of the contributions of AIBS to EOG. Both parties have agreed to a restructuring of the contractual arrangement that will afford more flexibility for NESCent to pursue its outreach initiatives while focusing the AIBS activities in key areas of collaboration. This restructuring will result in a shift in emphasis from policy to two specific research initiatives and greater emphasis on communication of NESCent-sponsored science.

1. Guiding principles of the Education and Outreach group

The mission of the NESCent Education and Outreach Group (EOG) is to provide leadership for evolution educators, to communicate results of NESCent science to the scientific community and the public, and to provide research in support of both of these initiatives.

The **communication** initiatives are intended to convey the results of the latest research in evolutionary biology to the general public and the evolutionary biology community, with a particular emphasis on NESCent-sponsored science. The EOG webpage has been integrated into the newly designed NESCent website. It will continue to be an active reference site for scientists, educators and the public and will include a biweekly “evolution in the news section.” EOG staff will take major responsibility for the new NESCent News portion of our website and our quarterly newsletter. They will work to disseminate evolutionary biology research to mainstream media outlets through a journalism fellows program; and continue to produce a resource CD to accompany the annual NABT symposium on an evolutionary biology topic co-sponsored by NESCent, AIBS and BSCS.

The **education** initiatives will promote improved quality of instruction in evolutionary biology, primarily in Universities and Colleges. We will convene working groups on applied evolution, and on the theory and practice of teaching evolution; work to incorporate NESCent-developed databases into exemplary curriculum resources; offer a distance education course on applied evolution; and address issues specifically related to historically minority universities and recruitment of under-represented groups into the field of evolutionary biology. In addition, we will provide a professional development program for NESCent post-docs, and install a visiting scientist outreach program.

Three focused **research** initiatives are directed at supporting improvement in the quality of formal and informal evolutionary biology education. We will investigate the extent of disparities in the opportunity to pursue evolutionary biology at Historically Minority Universities (HMUs) and research the impact on understanding of core concepts; generate a database of NSF-sponsored broader impact activities designed to inspire new researchers; and provide research support for the evolution working groups.

2. Examples of Major Education and Outreach Achievements in Year 2

The Evolution Education Working Group.

In pursuit of NESCent's mission to promote synthesis in relation to evolutionary biology, EOG hosted an important catalysis meeting of twenty-five evolution education experts July 10th and 11th, 2006 ("The Evolution-Education Group"). The individuals attending this meeting are listed in Appendix A.5, and represent a wide range of backgrounds and constituencies. They gathered to discuss the current state of evolution education in the United States, to identify the areas of greatest need over the next five to ten years, and to define the role that NESCent may play in promoting the pursuit of specific objectives. Ten years ago, a similar group, meeting in Berkeley, identified curricular support for high school teachers and development of coordinated teaching resources as immediate needs, and thereby catalyzed initiatives such as the Understanding Evolution website. The overwhelming sense of the NESCent meeting was that the most pressing need now is improvement in the quality of teacher education at all levels. To this end, NESCent will support a new targeted working group on Teaching Evolution that will be charged with identifying and promoting activities that facilitate improvements in the quality of teaching, primarily at the university level. The group will likely be coordinated by Craig Nelson (Emeritus Professor from Indiana University) with help from Sam Donovan (University of Pittsburgh). It will address such issues as incorporating new pedagogy into teacher education, raising awareness of inquiry-based learning methods and evolution simulators, improving access to online resources, and developing databases that can be used to generate exemplary curricular materials. John Jungck (Beloit College) has already taken steps to work with NESCent postdoctoral fellows Kirsten Fisher and Samantha Price to convert their databases into teaching materials. Our initial plan was for the larger Evolution-Education catalysis group to meet annually, but we will instead use our resources to support the working group in Teaching Evolution.

The NABT Symposium on Macroevolution.

NESCent and AIBS have agreed to partner each year on the presentation of an evolution-themed symposium at the annual conference of the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT). This forum provides an audience of several hundred highly motivated educators who are predominantly active in high schools and allows us to inform this community about recent advances in a particular topic in evolutionary biology. A summary of the symposium is available on our website (see <http://eog.nescent.org/NABTsymposium.htm>). This year, we put considerable effort into production of a professional CD on Macroevolution that was distributed free of charge to all attendees of the symposium. It has also been distributed at other venues, such as a teacher workshop offered by the education committee of the Society of Vertebrate Paleontology. The CD includes short video presentations by three NESCent-associated scientists (Greg Wray, Brian Wiegman and Samantha Price), links to materials supplied by the six prominent researchers who spoke at the Symposium (Nicole King, Nipam Patel, Jeffrey Levinton, Dave Jablonski, Philip Gingerich, and Scott Hodges), and various other materials relating to Macroevolution. The CD also includes an assessment tool, which will be used to guide the development of future CDs. The content of the CD can also be accessed at EOG's website (<http://eog.nescent.org/NABT/>).

The topic of the 2007 NABT symposium is Evolution and Human Health and we are coordinating with the upcoming NESCent sponsored catalysis meeting "Evolution in

Contemporary Human Populations: Medical, Genetic and Behavioral Implications” to identify potential speakers for the symposium as well as useful material for the CD.

The EEHMU Working Group.

EOG is responsible for a range of activities that promote minority involvement in evolutionary biology. A second meeting of the Evolution Education at Historically Minority Universities (EEHMU) Working Group was held on April 20th and 21st, 2006. New members from Barry University in Miami, FL, Colorado State University in Pueblo, CO, and North Carolina A&T University in Greensboro, NC, expanded the range of the group, and representatives from NCEAS (the National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis) and AIBS were also in attendance. Three notable outcomes of the meeting were:

EEHMU affirmed its support for continuation of the NESCent Targeted Sabbatical program and drafted a letter to the Director to this end, obtaining Dr Kathleen Smith’s commitment that so long as activities consistent with the EOG mission are identified, NESCent will endeavor to support sabbatical applications from HMU faculty.

A request that NESCent establish a Travel Award program to bring promising undergraduates to national evolution meetings, accompanied by mentors from both their home institution and a faculty member from a participating Research I school. To this end, EOG will commit \$5,000 per annum to the program, and seek a 2:1 financial match from Departments at Research I institutions, potentially sending 10 students a year to the annual SSE (or similar) meetings, in an arrangement that benefits the students, their mentors, and prospective graduate programs.

Dean Joseph Graves from North Carolina A&T University and Dr Camellia Okpodu from Norfolk State University took the lead in convincing EEHMU that there is an urgent need for evaluation of the magnitude of the evolution teaching disparity at HMUs in general and HBCUs in particular. The only way that Deans and Department Heads are likely to reverse the lack of institutional commitment to evolutionary biology is if they see hard data on a deficit in course offerings, and evidence that this may harm their graduates’ prospects. To this end, EOG will hire a research associate in 2007 to compare data from John Clamp’s (2005-2006 targeted sabbatical scholar) initial survey of teaching at HMUs with data from Liberal Arts and Research I Colleges. We will support the Doctoral research on this topic of a graduate student in the Educational Leadership and Policy Studies program at NC State, Mr Dewayne Branch.

EOG Participation in the SACNAS Conference

In October, 2006 the EOG group attended the annual conference of SACNAS (The Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science) where we organized and sponsored a panel discussion entitled “Exploring Careers in Evolutionary Biology and Ecology”. This session was well attended, primarily by underrepresented minority undergraduate students, although there were also graduate students, postdoctoral fellows and faculty members in attendance. Panelists included ecologists and evolutionary biologists representing a diversity of career paths (Research I universities, liberal arts colleges, government agencies and education/outreach groups) discussing the various career options that exist for students pursuing degrees in those fields.

Feedback from the session was overwhelmingly positive, and plans are currently underway to make this an annual event at SACNAS, as well as at other science conferences focused on

minority recruitment/advancement, such as ABRCMS and MANRRS. The program will also be expanded from a single panel discussion to a suite of activities, which might include events such as:

- Individual and group mentoring sessions at the conferences
- Field trips lead by an ecologist and/or evolutionary biologist to field sites of interest in the general vicinity of the conferences
- A “movie night” in which a feature film or documentary relevant to ecology/evolution would be shown in the evening at the conferences, followed by a discussion to be led by ecologists/evolutionary biologists on the meaning and impact of the film
- Another panel discussion similar to the one held recently at SACNAS

NESCent’s EOG group is currently in discussion with a number of groups who have already expressed an interest in collaborating on these future activities, including AIBS, the Ecological Society of America, NCEAS, NSF (Dr. Sonia Ortega), and the SSE Education Committee.

Scientist Professional Development at NESCent

EOG has taken a very active role in providing NESCent Postdoctoral Fellows with opportunities to develop their scholarship of teaching and learning, primarily through the development of a 9-part monthly seminar series. “The workshops have provided me with my first introduction to the philosophy of teaching/education, something that had been missing from my education so far. They have encouraged me to think about my teaching style/philosophy and to get involved in the education working groups coming to NESCent” (comment from current NESCent postdoctoral fellow). Furthermore, EOG staff provides a permanent resource for Fellows, meeting informally with them throughout the year to provide counseling, information and resources on various aspects of teaching, science outreach and career/professional development. In years 3 – 5, we will ask that all Fellows participate in the outreach activities of the center, in part for their own experience and further their ability to develop broader impact programs. At minimum we will ask that they give at least one lecture each year, generally at a smaller college. They will also be given the opportunity to use NESCent videoconferencing facilities to deliver distance learning guest lectures and seminars. At the request of the postdoctoral fellows, the scope of the professional development series will be slightly modified to include a broader range of topics related to professional development, and will include greater participation of NESCent senior scientists (Sabbatical Scholars, Triangle Scholars and Directors). Topics will include applying for your first job, grant proposal strategies, negotiation, and so forth.

3. Promotion of NESCent Science

Looking to the future, NESCent will place much greater emphasis on the promotion of NESCent-sponsored science now that this is in full bloom. To date, an interview with Kathleen Smith has been published in *BioScience*, and a writer visited NESCent in November to gather material for another full *BioScience* article on the Center and programs, to be published in the winter of 2007. An EOG member sits in on each NESCent working group and catalysis meeting and writes up a general summary of the meeting. These summaries are posted on the EOG web site for educators and the general public as well as on the main NESCent site for other scientists. We will work closely with the leaders of two or three working groups each year to produce greater exposure of their efforts for the public. For example, EOG staff worked with a local science writer to produce an article on the

Madagascar Biodiversity working group that was published on the Action Bioscience website (<http://www.actionbioscience.org/evolution/roberson.html>). EOG will produce press releases to be sent to EurekAlert, targeted journals, and universities before and after selected meetings. EOG will also work with journalism students at local Universities, in some cases helping them to write articles for publication in a variety of media outlets. An undergraduate or graduate student from Duke, UNC, or NCSU will also be recruited as an intern for this program. In addition, EOG promotes NESCent science at conferences and meetings through presentations, advertisements, brochures, and in some cases by staffing a booth (see Appendix A.15). After two years of operation, we have a strong sense of both our limitations and potential, and have switched our emphasis as appropriate to focus now on the areas of communication, education, and research. There is much to do, and we look forward with ambition to making a difference over the next three years.

4. EOG Personnel and Partnerships

Responsibility for EOG activities lies with NESCent Associate Director Greg Gibson, who supervises two full time education and outreach program managers, and an hourly undergraduate.

Kristin Jenkins is the NESCent Science Communication Manager, with primary responsibility for communication of evolutionary biology to the general public, focusing increasingly on NESCent science. In years 1&2 Jenkins was paid by AIBS on the subcontract to that organization. In years 3-5 her position will be moved to the core NESCent grant and she will assume the role of communications manager for NESCent. In this role Jenkins will (i) work with the Center Director to promote NESCent science to the general community. This will include working with local reporters and news outlets and coordination of a new science journalism program; (ii) work with leaders of working groups and catalysis meetings that lend themselves to outreach; (iii) establish a database of successful broader impact activities in the area of evolutionary biology; and (iv) work with the AIBS, specifically on an annual symposium on evolution for the National Association of Biology Teachers.

Jory Weintraub is the NESCent Science Education Manager, with primary responsibility for promotion of evolution education by fostering the academic development of NESCent scientists, and pursuing programs designed to improve the quality of evolution education offered at universities and colleges. He divides his time among (i) coordination of the in-house Post-Doctoral Professional Development program, including oversight of a traveling lecturer program; (ii) serving as liaison for the evolution working groups, including a new Teaching Evolution working group, the Evolution Education in Historically Minority Universities (EEHMU) working group, the SACNAS group and an Applied Evolution working group; (iii) supplying general support for post-doctoral and sabbatical research at NESCent; and (iv) organizing the travel award program proposed by the EEHMU group and designed to increase minority recruitment into evolutionary biology research programs.

Diane Bosnjak is the EOG webmaster. She is an undergraduate at NC State University and is employed by NESCent for between 10 and 15 hours per week. In regular consultation with Weintraub and Jenkins, Bosnjak updates the website with new materials (including a bi-weekly evolution in the news feature), links, video clips, and outreach materials arising from working groups.

In addition to EOG staff members, our efforts are aided by Dr. Joe Fail, who is the second targeted sabbatical scholar to be working on EOG materials. Fail is visiting for 12 months

from Johnson C. Smith University outside Charlotte, NC, and is working on the development of new curricular materials that introduce evolutionary concepts for elementary school students.

American Institute of Biological Sciences (AIBS)

The AIBS has been a key partner with EOG from the inception of this project, providing access to the evolution education community and potentially to policy makers in Washington DC. For the first two years of NESCent's grant, they have operated under a subcontract to NC State University that paid for salary and fringe for Kristin Jenkins, partial support for AIBS staff member Susan Musante, and covered costs associated with NESCent activities, including travel and publication charges for *BioScience* articles. As a result of our reorganized focus on communication, university education and outreach to under-represented groups, AIBS and NESCent leadership have agreed to restructure the arrangement so that AIBS is specifically contracted for targeted services. As mentioned above, Jenkins will move to employment directly by Duke University, and the remaining AIBS sub-contract will also be administered through Duke. There will no longer be any expectation that AIBS engages in public policy activities related to evolutionary biology.

5. Goals and Challenges for EOG in Years 3-5

In Years 3-5, EOG will place a high priority on three initiatives: minority recruitment and education, development of applied evolution resources for education, and assembly of a database of broader impact activities. We will implement two new programs in support of minority recruitment into the field of evolutionary biology. First, based on the recommendations of EEHMU, a pilot faculty-student matching program will be designed to bring senior undergraduate students from HMUs to national meetings accompanied by a faculty member from their home institution, and a faculty member from a Research I university. We will establish networks of HMU faculty and participating Research I Evolutionary Biology Departments, and request that the latter provide a 1:1 match for grants of \$500 to \$1,000, leveraging our funds to double the number of students who can attend meetings such as SMBE or SSE. There they will be introduced to contemporary research in a context that is likely to lead to successful recruitment to graduate school. Second, we will hire a research professional to perform a statistical comparison of the quantity and level of evolutionary biology that is taught at HMUs relative to non-HMU institutions. These data will be compiled into a report that will provide Deans and Department Heads at HMUs with hard data that they may consider when allocating resources to the teaching of evolutionary biology, and it will seed a graduate thesis on educational policy in this area.

Three further initiatives will promote the teaching of applied evolution. A NESCent working Group led by John Jungck (Beloit College) will meet for the first time in mid-December 2006 and twice more in 2007 to develop curricular materials integrating applied evolution at the undergraduate level. In parallel, a distance learning class on Evolution and Society will be offered for the first time at NC State University in the spring semester of 2007. The course will be taught by a postdoctoral associate in Associate Director Greg Gibson's laboratory, Dr. Lisa Goering, using the latest audio-visual technology and internet-based teaching methods. It will take David Mindell's "This Evolving World" as a text, showing students the impact of evolutionary biology on agriculture, medicine, environmental science, and forensics, among other topics. Furthermore, a new "Teaching Education" working group will be convened to examine pedagogy and evolutionary instruction in general. Together these activities will lead to the production of exemplary educational materials that

paint evolutionary biology in a positive light by promoting the practical applications of the science.

Another major goal for years 3 through 5 is to improve the broader impact experience for both researchers and the public. Ideally, both parties will find the experience engaging, enjoyable, and educational. Most researchers do not have any educational training, and many find themselves at a loss when faced with developing a broader impact statement. We plan to assemble a database of broader impact activities in evolutionary biology that researchers can use as a resource in designing their own outreach. Rather than simply compiling a list of activities, we will research and detail particularly successful programs. The project will also include suggestions and guidelines for researchers to help them identify new audiences, and construct novel and effective broader impact activities. We expect this project to be particularly helpful for new investigators.

EOG's plan for 5-year deliverables:

- a website that provides information about national evolution education resources
- a whitepaper for the NSF on educational disparities in historically minority universities and minority serving institutions
- database of broader impact activities and a coordinated database of contacts at historically minority universities and graduate and summer research programs in evolutionary biology
- initiatives to improve the use of educational theory in evolution teaching and to promote incorporation of applied evolution in teaching and research
- publications in the general media promoting NESCent science
- a distance-learning course in Applied Evolution
- professional development for NESCent scientists

D NESCENT ADMINISTRATION

The development of NESCent as a functioning center has continued in year 2. In year 1 we focused on hiring initial staff and renovating physical space, during year 2 significant effort was required to develop the administrative infrastructure that would allow a center with approximately 10 full time staff, 20 on site scientists and over 500 yearly visitors to function properly. Major year 2 administrative activities accomplishments include the following:

1. Meeting of the NESCent Senior Advisory Board

In April of 2006 we met with our Senior Advisory Board (membership in Appendix A.8) for very useful discussions regarding the reorganization, our current progress and priorities in years 2-5. In particular a significant amount of time was spent discussing the revised Informatics plan and ways that NESCent could go forward following the reorganization. A copy of the report of the Board is provided in Appendix D.1.

2. Duke University Provost's fund

We have secured independent funds from Duke University for the support of activities that will significantly enhance NESCent's function, but are outside the scope of the NSF grant. These funds will be applied to a number of activities that extend NESCent's impact. A major focus has been to develop activities that increase the participation of evolutionary biologists from the Triangle Universities in NESCent activities. One of the most important activities thus funded is the "Triangle Working Group" where we fund working groups composed largely of scientists from Triangle Universities. These proposals are reviewed by our Scientific Review Board, and are treated as regular NESCent working groups, but consist largely of faculty from local universities. These working groups bring local scientists to NESCent and introduce NESCent in-house scientists to many local evolutionary biologists. Thus far we have funded a group on molecular and fossil approaches to evolutionary time (Julia Clark, NCSU, lead), and one on genomic patterns of processes of introgression (Marcy Uyenoyama, Duke, lead). This latter proposal is notable as it includes a number of faculty from North Carolina Central University, a local historically minority serving institution.

In addition, a planned series of seminars and workshops in which major external speakers are invited to the Center will be funded from this source. This series will serve 3 functions: it will draw attention to the center in the surrounding community, it will aid in postdoctoral development (they are organizing the series); it will bring the center to the attention of major evolutionary biologists nationally. A number of experimental outreach activities have been funded from the Provost's fund, including hiring free lance science writers to write articles in the general and scientific press about NESCent activities, developing a science internship program of local journalism students and creating the educational CD distributed at the NABT conference in coordination with the symposium on Macroevolution. The Provost's fund has allowed us to purchase furniture for our large seminar room, and to equip a small library for the use of NESCent scientists. Finally, these funds have provided money for a variety of social events for in-house, community and visiting scientists.

3. Staffing

In year 2 NESCent hired one additional staff assistant for support of office, financial and meeting activities. In addition, we are in the process of hiring an additional staff member for administrative and IT support (webmaster, database curation, help-desk functions). This

staff member will be paid for by funds from Duke University. As NESCent continues to grow we will need to continually assess the sufficiency of our administrative, logistical and informatics staffing. Already we have approximately 20 meetings scheduled in the Center during the next 6 months (Appendix D.2).

4. International collaborations

Evolutionary biology is an international exercise and it is important for NESCent to identify potential international collaborations. Two such collaborations, begun in year 1 of the Center's existence by Cliff Cunningham, are maturing. First, we are sponsoring, with the ARC-NZ Research Network for Vegetative Function, and Postdoctoral Fellow Amy Zanne, a working group on a synthetic study of the evolution of wood structure and function. In addition we have had discussions with David Lambert of the Allan Wilson Centre for Molecular Ecology and Evolution in Auckland, New Zealand about future collaborations. We expect this discussion to solidify during the Evolution meeting in New Zealand in June, 2007.

5. Administrative Infrastructure

Administrative Database

One of the major goals this year has been to develop an administrative database to manage core Center functions and to facilitate reporting activities. The database is expected to encompass the submission and review of proposals, information on awarded projects, scientific products, participants, meetings, visitors, etc. The functional and user interface requirements, which were initially inspired by the data model employed by NCEAS' administrative database, were extensively reviewed by a group consisting of the main stake holders among the staff and those from the Informatics team responsible for planning and executing the project. This process ensured that the requirement specifications match the operations and requirements of the Center.

The project is currently in its implementation phase, with the data model having been finalized and on-going work focusing on implementing user-interfaces and server-side middleware. Completion of the project is expected within the second quarter of 2007, so that the annual reporting cycle in 2007 will be fully supported by the database. The development of this database has occupied a considerable percentage of the core Informatics staff effort over the past several months.

The NESCent Website

The Senior Advisory Board indicated that an immediate goal should be "a NESCent Website that is informative, accessible, and which serves as a resource to the evolution community." To this end, the Center contracted the services of Duke University's Web Solutions Team (WeST). Over a series of consultations, Duke's WeST developed from scratch a design and layout for the Center's website that is internally consistent, visually appealing, easily navigable and, most importantly, easily extensible and updateable by Center staff. In parallel, we conceived a site map with the aim of presenting all current and past activities and products of the Center in a comprehensive and up-to-date fashion. A number of pages including current and past science as well as calendars of events and meetings will be driven dynamically by the data content of the administrative database, which ensures that the presented information is comprehensive, up-to-date, and may be queried in a flexible

manner. We will migrate most content from the old to the new website by January 2007. Full functionality will be dependent on the development and population of our database.

Survey for NESCent Visitors

An online survey was established for participants in NESCent meetings. This survey primarily requests feedback concerning the logistical and informatics support through NESCent. Although participants have expressed very high levels of satisfaction with our logistics and informatics support, responses to this survey have already helped us modify aspects of Center function, logistics and informatics support.

Project Management Software

We are in the process of implementing project management software for tracking all activities associated with group logistics and informatics, postdoctoral and sabbatical fellows, personnel and review dates, and call for proposal timelines.

Orientation Material and Development of Policies and Procedures

An orientation document for new Center visitors and a Policies and Procedures document were developed. These incorporated local policy, as well as NSF and Duke University requirements and are posted on the website.

Development of Logistical Support for Meetings

In year 2 over 500 visitors passed through NESCent in various supported and hosted meetings and we expect that number to increase by 50-100% in years 3 and 4 as we host a full array of meetings. In December 2006 alone we expect > 60 visitors in NESCent sponsored activities. During year 2 we developed and implemented logistical procedures for hosting scientific meetings. Significant effort was placed into developing procedures and policies that were efficient, cost effective, met federal and Duke University regulations, and provided Center visitors with the best possible experience. Major actions included

- developed a series of processes for meeting support, including financial practices, and logistical and IT support that allow visiting scientists to focus on science
- negotiated Federal rates for an upgraded hotel rooms with free wireless access
- negotiated reduced rates for shuttle service to and from the airport
- negotiated free shuttle service from the hotel to NESCent and to area restaurants
- all travel arrangements made through our travel agent. Unusual travel requests must be approved in advance by NESCent following Duke and NSF policies
- reimbursements processed from 2-5 days after receiving original receipts
- developed process for tracking justification and airfares for international participants

6. Building the NESCent Community

We have developed a number of activities to improve the sense of community of onsite NESCent scientists and staff. These include a number of social events including happy hours, meals, picnics and the like. We are also hosting social events so that the visitors from each working group or catalysis meeting may informally interact with onsite scientists, to increase the likelihood of broader collaboration and impact. Funding for social activities is provided by money from the Duke University Provost Fund.

To advance further community building activities, a NESCent Retreat was held in September and included all members of NESCent. The morning session consisted of a postdoc orientation (postdoc scientific expectations and the postdoc review process, NESCent informatics support, Education/Outreach goals and expectations for participation by postdocs, the EOG professional development series, and a brief review of NESCent policies and procedures). Afternoon sessions included a NESCent town hall meeting open to all Center staff and scientists in which ways that the Center might be improved were discussed. Finally the retreat was followed by a scientific program and dinner for postdoctoral fellows.

7. Administrative Goals and Challenges in Years 3-5

We believe we are close to accomplishing many of the most important administrative infrastructure tasks that must be in place to make the Center function appropriately. However, several challenges remain.

1. As NESCent continues to increase its activities, in terms of the number and diversity of meetings and individuals supported by the Center, we must continually reassess our staffing needs. An organizational chart for NESCent as a whole is included as Appendix D.2. We are already hiring one additional individual for informatics and administrative support from money provided by Duke University. It is not clear if we can continue to provide the same level of logistics, financial, and most importantly informatics support with our current staff if the traffic to the center increases at the rate we expect.
2. Ensuring proper overall leadership remains a concern. The SAB advised Duke University to recruit a full time Director for the Center, and we endorse this recommendation. Discussions are ongoing with Duke University administration about the timing, scope and mechanisms for such a search and appointment. This activity will like occupy significant time in the coming year.
3. Finally, one of the greatest administrative challenges facing us is resolution of the proper role of our Senior Advisory Board. The function of the Advisory Board, in particular its reporting responsibility to NSF, has been a source of conflict, which places the Center Directors in a difficult position. Currently the NSF Program Officers and the Advisory Board members have very different views of the role of this panel, and this conflict has reduced the effectiveness of our interaction with the Board.

The current Board was constituted with the impression that they would be providing frank advice on Center functions, outreach, impact and programs to the NESCent Directors. However, they have also been asked to provide a detailed written review of Center activities, which is given to the Program Officers at NSF. The current members of the Board do not accept this role, and our discussions with the Board have been overly dominated by consideration of the kind of report that NSF Program Officers expect. We believe our interaction with this Board will be much more useful to us if this question is resolved, and request that the site visit and project review help resolve this issue. We suggest the following possible solutions:

- 1) NSF and the Center Directors appoint a new Advisory Board, with the explicit understanding that this board will report in writing to the Directors and to NSF Program Officers, and thus serve in both advisory and review functions.
- 2) NESCent moves to a process that resembles the one in place at NCEAS where the Board serves as an advisory group to the NCEAS Director and Deputy Director, with no formal

communication to the NSF (beyond approval of additional members). Within this model we can see two options:

A) Following the NCEAS model and collapsing the Advisory Board and Science Review Board into a single board, which both reviews proposals, and advises the Center on activities ranging from “prosaic logistic issues (e.g., web content), to more serious and comprehensive topics such as new directions for the Center” (quote from NCEAS administrative document, provided by Jim Reichman).

B) Continuing to keep the Boards separate, but slightly reconstituting the Advisory Board to balance more effectively Science and Synthesis, Informatics and Education and Outreach advice to Center Directors.